

Original Research Article

Determine Guests' Awareness of Sustainable Green Practices in the Selected Hotels, South West Hotels (Nigeria)

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Abstract

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In all aspects of human existence, sustainability is a worldwide requirement. A sustainable approach to a pleasant environment is required in all sectors of human activity, including hotel amenities and services. The goal of this study was to analyze sustainable green practices in hotels in order to raise hotel managers' and tourists' knowledge of green practices for sustainable hotel amenities and tourism growth. The data for this study was collected using a structured questionnaire administered using purposive sampling. Each of the 20 hotels selected for this study received eleven (11) questionnaires, one for hotel managers and ten for guests, totaling 220 questionnaires. Descriptive and inferential statistical tests were used to examine the data. In several hotels, visitors' awareness of green measures was assessed. Out of the twenty-two (22) mentioned sustainable green facilities, five (5) variables generated the highest mean between (1.80) and (2.90). This indicates that guest awareness of green practices in the hotel is limited to energy-saving bulbs (2.90), low-flow water in the bathroom and toilet, reusable plastics, towels, cutlery, and bedding (2.70), eco-friendly retail (e-commerce or transact) (2.80), repair and refurbishment (1.80), and purchase of local or indigenous food in the hotel kitchen (2.30). The Chi-Square test revealed a significant connection ($P = 0.000$) between preference for green practices and hotel awareness of green practices. However, there is a substantial link between respondents' preference for green activities and their age ($P = 0.000$), marital status ($P = 0.000$), and degree of education ($P = 0.000$). To maintain a sustainable environment and protection of our natural resources, the research advises that sustainable green practices be incorporated into our society as our mother tongue, expanded into hotel facilities, and utilized as a standard for hotel licensing.

Keywords: Hotel facilities, Eco-friendly, Green facilities awareness and Sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability is a global need in all aspects of human daily requirements and a requirement in all human activities, including hotel facilities and services that require a sustainable approach for a friendlier

environment. Green practices are one of the driving reasons behind the development of sustainable hotel facilities, according to several papers, which is a factor assessed in this study.

Green practices, also known as going green, are the pursuit of knowledge and practices that can lead to more environmentally friendly, ecologically responsible decisions and lifestyles, which can help to protect the environment and sustain its natural resources for current and future generations (Middletown, 2019). (Lee *et al.* 2016).

The overall energy consumed and the amount of natural resources utilized, as well as the environment's sustainability and waste disposal, all have an influence on the ecosystem, according to Lisa (2019). Green or eco-friendly amenities in the hotel business are also on the rise throughout the world, according to Mbasera *et al.* (2016), and customers are growing more conscious of the need for eco-friendly facilities.

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Eco-friendly practices were concluded to be an ecologically responsible medium that reduces human ecological footprint or demand on natural resources and ecosystems in which human life coexists based on the framework presented by the authors above. Outdoor apparel brands, dispensed drinks, reusable bedding and towels, eco-friendly cleaning, installation of solar energy sources or solar appliances, recycling water and kitchen waste into biogas, and many more facilities are considered eco-friendly hotel amenities.

Forests support 1.6 billion people, including 70 million indigenous peoples, and they are home to more than 80% of all terrestrial animals, plants, and insects, according to the European Environmental Agency (2017). The hotel business, according to Lisa (2019), is the world's largest industry, has a substantial environmental effect, and is intimately tied to international tourism, which brought in \$856 billion in 2007.

Modern technology is encroaching on our environment, particularly in the creation of hotel facilities, and future generations and their demands are becoming obsolete. As a result, it is necessary to focus on ecosystem sustainability and natural resource management (Adegbola, 2019). While constructing hotel facilities, eco-friendly procedures will be utilized to limit the industry's impact on the environment (Rob 2019).

According to Ridhima *et al.* (2018), as the hospitality industry becomes more competitive, it is critical for hotels to attract market forces by using green marketing strategies. According to Lisa (2019), eco-friendly hotels and lodging facilities consume significantly less energy than those that are not, and clients choose an eco-friendly hotel because of the growing worldwide

awareness of climate change (Leal *et al.* 2016). Rob (2019) stated that eco-friendly practices such like energy saving and water conservation should be applied efficiently in guest rooms, laundries, kitchens, pools, and spas to decrease natural resource use. Customers' or guests' and other stakeholders' growing concern about the state of the ecosystem is a worldwide problem, which is why hotels are implementing environmentally friendly efforts to limit the negative impact of their operations on the environment. Eco-friendly services, such as hotel eco-washing, sell products or services that are based on true environmental benefits. These facilities are ecologically friendly and absorbable, having no detrimental effects on the environment. Eco-marketing is mostly practical, honest, and transparent, and it means that a product or service meets certain criteria, including:

- Sustainable fashion.
- Free of toxic materials or ozone-depleting substances.
- Full recycled initiatives, able to be recycled and/or purchase products made from recycled Materials, or use products made from recycled materials.
- Interior decoration made from renewable materials (such as bamboo).
- Policy of repair and refurbishing rather than disposable, upholstered, or up-cycled furniture.
- Installing solar panels as an energy source or purchasing a solar electronics appliance
- Eco-friendly landscaping.
- Organic food.
- Eco-friendly retail (e-commerce or transact).
- Eco-friendly beauty Saloon (use of locally made hair cream).
- Eco-friendly venues, materials, and accommodations.
- Eco-friendly interior decoration and fittings.
- Process waste should be reduced.
- Occupancy sensors (Key Cards, Thumb Identification or finger print, Eye contact).
- Wind energy (Windvain,)
- Compact efflorescent lights
- Low flow fixture in the bath room.

The eco-friendly environment encourages relaxation and makes man closer to nature for their wellbeing and conservation of human environment for sustainable use. The great strides toward bringing in eco-friendly practices and earning green certifications in hospitality sector is trending (Lisa 2019). There can be active drivers of sustainable green environment if there is proper awareness of the importance of green landscaping for health of the guest and human environment (Adegbola, 2019).

The benefit of sustainable eco-friendly facilities for hotel include:

- Energy efficient products and practices also save money while helping the planet.

- Reduction of hotel water and sewer costs can be cut by 25-30 percent just by installing water-efficient fixtures.
- It offers opportunities to gain an advantage over competitors because of friendliness approach.
- It enhances good environmental regulations (Dalibi et al., 2017)

Hotel facilities have a significant impact on nature and the ecosystem, and as a result, global warming, climate change, ozone depletion, pollution, high consumption of natural resources, and an increase in the amount of solid waste generated by human activities have recently become global threats. According to Ibrahim (2019), international cuisines and unusual menu items have infiltrated the local market, displacing ethnic and traditional cuisines. If this trend continues, traditional cuisine's identity and the long-term viability of local culinary culture would be jeopardized. As part of the tourist business, hotels have a considerable environmental impact. While the magnitude and breadth of hotels' environmental effect indicate a pressing need to address this issue. The question is whether hotels understand the importance of environmentally friendly activities in their businesses (Mbasera et al., 2016). In Nigeria, environmental deterioration is a danger to long-term economic development (Ishmael et al., 2015). If hoteliers do not implement green practices, waste production will increase, negative environmental impacts will worsen, and local purchases of organic and locally grown food will be extremely low. Furthermore, hoteliers will not adhere to national and international sustainability legislation, and will not engage in responsible business practices. This will result in a higher overall ecological and carbon footprint, as well as continued depletion of natural resources and energy. It is a worldwide issue, as environmental sensitivity is becoming increasingly important. Because of the global warming effect and the trend of hotel industry expansion, eco-friendly amenities in Nigerian hotels must be investigated, particularly in (South West) Akure, as a case study, because the sector's influence on environment and ecosystem holistically cannot be overstated (Adegbola *et.al* 2020). According to Mbasera (2015), hotels have the highest detrimental impact on the environment of any commercial facility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This research was conducted in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria's south west. Twenty hotels were chosen for this study, accounting for 13% of all hotels in Ondo State. They focused on the three senatorial districts and targeted towns (Owo, Akure, Idanre, and Oke-Igbo) with

a particular focus on hotels near tourist destinations. The hotel ratings range from 1 to 4, with a maximum of (5 to 25) years of operation, number of rooms, and distance from the tourist attraction to the hotel and restaurant capacity. The study was analyzed utilizing descriptive and inferential methods, including frequency tables, charts, and percentages, as well as Pearson's Product Moment Correlation in SPSS Version 20. The acquired data was analyzed using Chi-Square testing.

Methods of Data Collection and Analysis

This study included both primary and secondary data. Field observations, field surveys, and interviews provided the primary data. Secondary data is frequently gathered through books, journals, and hotel documents. The study included data from hotels in four towns (Owo, Akure, Idanre, and Oke-Igbo) and three LGAs (Ose, Akure South(s), and Ile-Oluji/Oke-Igbo) that reflect Ondo State's three senatorial districts (see details on Table 1.0).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table below shows how visitors' green practices were evaluated. This implies that visitor understanding of green practices at the hotel is restricted to energy-saving bulbs (2.90), low-flow water in the bath and toilet, reusable plastics, towels, cutlery, and bedding (2.70), eco-friendly retail (e-commerce or transact) (2.80), repair and refurbishment (1.80), and purchasing of local or indigenous cuisine in the hotel kitchen (2.30). Apart from the prevalent green practices in the selected hotels, guests' awareness of green practices in the selected hotels reveals that visitors are unaware of the variables specified as green practices in this study. This was supported by Hamilton (2020), who stated that customers are becoming more aware of green practices, hotels in Ennistymon, Irish Land work on the hotel's hydroelectric plant from the nearby river Inagh, which prevented 550 tonnes of carbon from being released into the environment, and that renewable energy was driven by demand from customers looking for green places to visit and stay. According to (Mbasera, 2015), energy savings can be achieved by using energy-saving light bulbs such as compact fluorescent light bulbs and energy-star efficient HVAC systems, as well as a rise in environmental awareness, emphasizing the low-carbon era today. Green tourism will be the new direction for tourism's future development (Lee *et al.*, 2016). Lisa, (2019), who stated that the Hilton Palacio del Rio hotel with 480 rooms saved 6 million gallons of water in eight months after installing dual-flush toilets and toilet tank fill diverters, also can reduce water use and toilet, reusable plastics, towel, cutlery, and beddings, and eco-friendly

Table 1. Tourism Destinations in Ondo State

Town	Local Government Area	Tourism Attraction/ Festival	Senatorial District
Owo	Ose	Olowo Palace- Artifact/Museum	Ondo-North
Akure	Akure South	Dejis Palace & Museum/T.A Afolayan wildlife park	Ondo- Central
Idanre	Akure South	Idanre Hill	Ondo- Central
Oke- Igbo	Ile-Oluji/Oke-Igbo	Forest of the Almighty(Igbo Olodumare)	Ondo-South

Source: Author's Compilation, 2021.

Table 2. List of the Hotel Selected and the locations

S/N	Hotel Localities	Names of the Hotel
1.	Akure	Futa Scholar's lodge.
2.		Groovy Hotel, Okeljebu.
3.		Bliss world Hotel Akure.
4.		Finger Print Hotel, Oba-ile Akure.
5.		Heritage Continental Hotel Akure.
6.	Owo	Mydas Hotel and Resort
7.		The Chancery Hotel
8.		First Molack hotel
9.		The Finger Prints Hotel
10.	Idanre	Lilojo Motel and Garden
		Green Park hotel, Oke-Aro, Akure
		Start Light Hotel, Alalde Idanre.
		Hill Top Hotel Odode, Idanre.
		Rock Valley Hotel Idanre.
		Raphilo Hotel, Oke- Aro Akure.

Table 3. Determine guests' awareness of sustainable green practices in the selected hotels, South West Hotels (Nigeria).

S/N	Hotels Green practices	Yes	%	NO	%	Mean	St.Dev
1.	Energy saving bulbs	19	95	1	5	2.900	0.4472
2.	Low flow water in the bath room and toilet.	17	85	3	15	2.700	0.73270
3.	Reusable Plastics, towel, cutleries, and beddings	17	85	3	15	2.700	0.73270
4.	Recycling water Process	0	0	20	100	1.000	0.00000
5.	Up-cycling of kitchen waste/ Waste control	0	0	20	100	1.000	0.00000
6.	Dispense beer and beverages.	0	0	20	100	1.000	0.00000
7.	Trees and Shrubs	6	30	14	70	1.550	0.95145
8.	Solar energy sources/installations	3	15	17	85	1.300	0.73270
9.	Eco-friendly landscaping	4	20	16	80	1.400	0.82717
10.	Plant that attract birds and butterflies.	0	0	20	100	1.000	0.00000
11.	Up-cycled Furniture(s).	1	15	19	95	1.100	0.44721
12.	Repair and Refurbishing.	8	40	12	60	1.800	1.00525
13.	Eco-friendly retails (e-commerce or transact).	18	90	2	10	2.800	0.61559
14.	Presence of wildlife.	0	0	20	100	1.000	0.00000
15.	Paper Straw.	0	0	20	100	1.000	0.00000
16.	Presence of rock, brook and rivers	3	15	17	85	1.300	0.73270

Table 3. Continue

17.	Low Carbon environment	1	5	19	95	1.100	0.44721
18.	Local food/Indigenous food hotel kitchen	13	65	7	35	2.300	0.97872
19.	Local interior decoration(Window mat, Can chair)	3	15	17	85	1.300	0.60481
20.	Refillable shampoos and conditioners.	3	15	17	85	2.000	1.02598
21.	Bio-degradable control for Oil-spillage	4	20	16	80	1.400	0.82078
22.	Eco-friendly flooring	3	15	17	85	1.300	0.73270

Scale and symbol codes: Yes= (2); No=(1), The desired mean score values ($x \geq 2.50$).

Source: Field Work 2021.

Table 4: Relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and constraints to green practices

Variables	Chi Square (χ)	Sig. value	Decision
Awareness	216.398	0.000	Significant

The table below shows there is a significant relationship between preference for green practices and the respondents' age ($P=0.000$), marital status ($P=0.000$) and education level ($P=0.000$).

Table 5. Relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and constraints to green practices

Variables	Chi Square (χ)	Sig. value	Decision
Age	276.593	0.000	Significant
Marital status	104.591	0.000	Significant
Education level	198.102	0.000	Significant

retails (e-commerce or transact), and local food/Indigenous food hotel kitchen supported that Nigeria hotels are not left out. There is, however, still potential for development. Nigerian Hotel Blog 2020 (retrieved on October 3, 2020). Trees and shrubs, solar energy sources/installations, eco-friendly landscaping, plants that attract birds and butterflies, up-cycled furniture, presence of wildlife, Paper Straw, presence of natural features such as rock, brooks, and rivers, low carbon environment, local interior decoration (window mat, Can chair), refillable shampoos and hair conditioners, bio-degradable control for oil spillage, and eco-friendly flooring were not available. It was not a standard requirement as part of the essential facilities to improve the hotel's enabling eco-friendly atmosphere. This is reinforced by Stemberk et al. (2018), who state that environmental sustainability must be strongly integrated into the system until it becomes a mother tongue, taught as a language in society, and where people have a good attitude toward nature and their surroundings. The notion that environmental sustainability may promote a company's success is convincing if knowledge, understanding, and respect for our world become vital with each subsequent generation. According to Hamilton (2020), hotel green measures like as recycling, reusing towels, temperature management, organic cuisine selections, and electric car charging stations have an effect on visitor patronage.

RESULT OF THE HYPOTHESIS OF THE FINDINGS

Hypothesis Testing

The result shows there is a significant relationship between preference for green practices and awareness of green practices at the hotels ($P=0.000$). Table 4 and 5

CONCLUSION

Reusable towels, reusable cutlery, renewable energy, reusing bathroom water for irrigation/wetting, reusing laundry water to wash vehicles and clean up the water closet (toilet), reusing nylon bags, shredding used papers, tree planting, and reusing kitchen water and waste for soil nutrient/animal feeds are all examples of common green practices adopted as patterns or ways of life based on the environment and indigenous knowledge. As a result, the researcher defines "green practice" as a portion of everyday actions that are intentionally considered to ensure reuse or conservation of resources for future use. It is the process of transforming and preserving something for future use. These data clearly demonstrate that in the selected hotels, they determine guests' awareness of sustainable green practices in the selected hotels. Apart from the widespread green

practices in the selected hotels, guests' knowledge of green practices in the selected hotels suggests that visitors are unfamiliar with the variables defined as green practices in this study.

RECOMMENDATION

As a result, I recommend that professional advice in the selection of hotel facilities be followed. The populace is being educated on sustainable green practices as well as conservation. There is a need to stress the significant effect of inadequate sustainable green facilities in hotels on the human environment. Mutual relationships between the local community and hotel establishments should be encouraged. Cultural effects and African superstitions about harnessing biodiversity for the human environment should be erased.

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